

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS SAMSUNG MOBILES

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ABSTRACT

The company has a very advanced research and development department, which has helped it grow into one of the most innovative companies in the world. Samsung that Regarded as a global leader in the consumer electronics industry, Samsung focuses on producing and marketing a widerange of electronic goods. With a high level of brand recognition, the Samsung brand has grown immensely in popularity globally. With its highly advanced research and development department,the corporation has become one of the most innovative in the world of business. Samsung has developed numerous successful goods over the years, including its Samsung line, as part of its ongoing effort to diversify its product offering. This creative organization creates new goods to meet evolving customer needs. Additionally, it is a highly tech-focused business that constantly enhances its technological acquisition and infrastructure. It makes use of cutting-edge technologyto help it develop fresh, cutting-edge products for its clients and draw them away from competitors like Apple and Lenovo. Despite its achievements, Samsung still faces a number of difficulties, including growing competition, declining smartphone sales in its primary market of the United States, and the possibility of a corona virus pandemic. Samsung, brand satisfaction, customer satisfaction. As a global leader in consumer electronics, Samsung specializes in the production and marketing of a wide range of product The Samsung brand is highly recognized and has grown in popularity across the globe. As part of its ongoing effort to diversify its product line, Samsung has developed several successful goods throughout the years, including its Samsung.

Keywords: Samsung mobiles, Samsung galaxy ,Customer satisfaction Samsung users.

INTRODUCTION

Samsung, South Korean company that is one of the world's largest producers of electronic devices. Samsung specializes in the production of a wide variety of consumer and industry electronics, including appliances, digital media devices, semiconductors, memory chips, and integrated systems. Lee Byung - Chull established the Samsung corporation on March 1, 1938, as a food trade firm. In the beginning, he traded noodles and other items made in and aroundTaegu, Korea, and exported them to China and its provinces Customers are aware of the most recent features offered by various providers in their mobile phones as well as their costs. These days, communication is essential to daily existence. The domains of telecommunications have seen unprecedented technical advancements recently. The goal of these advancements is to offer clients new services that satisfy different needs according on how they use them for their utilizationfor their benefit. In the modern day, mobile phones have evolved from their primary function of communication to an extension of the user's identity More information regarding the competitors and the competition is provided by this study. The main topic of this survey was "Customer satisfaction towards Samsung mobiles.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

- To Research the customer issues and view points about Samsung mobile devices.
- The study the factors be considered while buying the Samsung smart phones to know the satisfaction towards Samsung smart phones.
- To study about the popularity of Samsung mobile phones among different customer

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The study was carried out in the Coimbatore district, and a sample of 150 individuals was selected.
- The study is limited to Samsung users.
- The study will last for six months.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study projects goal of examining customer behavior in connection to service quality and satisfaction with reference to the Samsung Mobile Company, a research problem has been chosen. Currently, there is fierce competition among phone companies in the mobile sector. This study will aid in learning more about the market variables influencing consumers to anticipate an issue the brand may encounter. Every business's ability to satisfy its customers is essential to its success.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

- Customers who are happy with a brand are more likely to stick with it, purchase further Samsung goods, and refer others to it.
- The distinction between surviving and thriving in terms of customer satisfaction.

SCOPE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

- This survey provides information about what features should be changed and how consumers feel about the Samsung mobile phone
- Samsung mobile phones have cutting-edge designs and the latest technologies in terms of Samsung mobile concepts.
- The primary study's scope is the company's knowledge, service quality, product, and customer satisfaction.

RESERCH METHODOLOGY

The method by which data and information are gathered in order to make business decisions. Because it describes information and traits related to the mobile phone population, the project's study design is descriptive in nature. Studying research methodology means learning using questionnaire survey, and tools analysis in addition to picking up knowledge about various research approaches.

RESERCH DESIGN

The process used to collect information and data for the purpose of making business decisions. The research design of the project is descriptive as it describes data and characteristics association with the population using mobile phones. Research methods are the techniques and tools by which you research a subject or a topic. Research methodology involves the learning of various techniques to conduct research and acquiring knowledge to perform tests, experiments, surveys, and critical analysis.

SAMPLE TECHNIQUE

In this research use random sampling method and data should be collected through the questionnaire. A convenience sample is a type of non-probability sampling method where the sample is taken from a group of people easy to contact or to reach.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size will depend on factors such as the population size, desired level of confidence. A samplesize of 150 response. From the people to ensure the customer satisfaction towards in Samsung mobiles.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The study covers the period of three months.

GEOGRAPHICAL AREA

The geographical area is Coimbatore, a city in the state of TamilNadu , India.

REVIEW OF LITERTURE

- ❖ **Assaari and Karia** (2000) held the opinion that customer service and satisfaction have been crucial components of the cellular sector in their work titled "Churn Management towards Customer Satisfaction; A Case of Cellular operations in Malaysia." It is imperative for cellular service providers to guarantee that their technology offers the greatest customer service available in the market. It is said that making investments in technology and people enables businesses to offer the greatest customer service possible both now and in the future.
- ❖ **Avnish Bansall's 2005**, "Cell Phones Taking Control of Our Lives," India is the world's fastest-growing mobile communication market. It was among the first countries to use the Global System for Mobile Communication (GSM) technology, and in 2005, there were over 30 million GSM users nationwide—a 100% increase from 2004. Furthermore, there were more than 10 million users of Code- Division Multiple Access (CDMA). Third generation (3G) technology should be widely adopted in India in order to keep up with the rest of the globe.
- ❖ **Das** (2021)¹⁸ conducted an empirical study using a survey approach to determine what factors young customers in Odisha, India's coastal districts consider when making mobile handset purchases. According to the survey, young consumers, women, recent college graduates, students, and city dwellers all strongly preferred phones with sleek designs, cutting-edge value added features, and enjoyable user experiences over those with a well-known brand.

SIMPLE PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS

Gender

PARTICULAR	NO.OF.RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE
Male	63	42
Female	87	58
Transgender	1	0
Total	150	100
Age group		
Below 20	62	41.33
21-30	50	33.33
31-40	30	20
Above 40	8	5.34
Total	150	100
Why To Choose Samsung Mobile Phones		
Due to price	16	10
Due to the quality	84	56
Due to the design	29	20
Due to the service	21	14
Total	150	100

INTERPRETATION

- ❖ Out of 150 Response the data of presents demographic distribution based on genderrespondents among the response 42% are identify the male while 58% are identity as female and 1% Identify as Transgender.
- ❖ Out of 150 Response 41.33% of the respondents are below the age of 20, 33.33% of the respondents are between the age of 21 to 30, 20% of the respondents are between the age group 31 to 40 and 5.34% the respondents are above the age of 40.
- ❖ Majority of the responses come from students, constituting 63% of the total .Employees and others make up 16% and 12% of the responses, respectively. Businesses have the smallest representation, contributing 9% of the total responses.

FRIEDMAN RANKING

Particulars	Ranking
Camera quality	1
Display quality	2
Brand loyalty	3
Service quality	4
price	5
Battery life	6
Features	7
Performance	8
Discount	9
Availability of different colors	10

INTERPETATION

A Friedman ranking tool that can be used to understand numerous project characteristics, like assessing pricing, battery life, features, performance, availability of multiple colours, brand loyalty, camera quality, display quality, and service quality. Researchers can determine which elements have the greatest influence or are favoured by respondents by using this statistical study. It indicates that respondents value camera quality more than other factors, for example, if it is ranked highest. Price, on the other hand, may not be as relevant to them when making decisions if it receives a lower rating.

CHI-SQUARE TEST

Income* Why To Chosen Samsung Mobile

	value	df	Asymp. Sig.(2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	1.913	1	.167
Continuity correction	.819	1	.365
Likelihood Ratio	3.329	11	.068
Fisher's exact test			
Linear –by-Linear Association	1.900	1	.168
N of Valid Cases	150		

Gender* Age group

	value	df	Asymp. Sig.(2-sided)
Pearson chi-square	1.453	2	.484
Likelihood Ratio	2.614	2	.271
Linear-by –Linear Association	.576	1	.448
N of valid cases	150		

INTERPETATION

❖ The chi-square statistic of 77.835 and 2 degrees of freedom, the associated p-value is very low ($p = .000$). This indicates a significant association between the variables. There is significant evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no association or trend among the variables being analyzed.

❖ This is the most common chi-square test statistic. It measures the extent of the discrepancy between observed and expected values in a contingency table. In your case, the chi-square value is 1.913 with 1 degree of freedom and a p-value of .167

❖ 90 This is another statistic used in the chi-square test, often used for nested models. In your output, the Likelihood Ratio Chi-Square value is 2.614, with 2 degrees of freedom, and the associated p-value is .167.

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Gender	Between Groups	.158	1	.158	1.256	.264
	Within Groups	18.615	148	.126		
	Total	18.773	149			
Occupation	Between Groups	.084	1	.084	.268	.606
	Within Groups	46.210	148	.312		
	Total	46.293	149			
Age group	Between Groups	1.214	1	1.214	3.525	.062
	Within Groups	50.979	148	.344		
	Total	52.193	149			
Marital status	Between Groups	.188	1	.188	1.393	.240
	Within Groups	19.972	148	.135		
	Total	20.160	149			
Education qualification	Between Groups	.073	1	.073	.809	.370
	Within Groups	13.427	148	.091		
	Total	13.500	149			
Income	Between Groups	.314	1	.314	1.912	.169
	Within Groups	24.280	148	.164		
	Total	24.593	149			

INTERPRETATION

The analysis of variance for several variables, including gender, occupation, age group, marital status, level of education, and income, is displayed in the ANOVA findings. Based on the sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean square, F-value, and significance level (Sig.), each variable is examined. The variability within groups and the variability between groups are compared using the F-value. Since all of the variables' p-values (Sig.) are higher than the traditional cut off of 0.05 in this study, none of the variables exhibit a significant effect, suggesting that any group differences are more likely the result of random variation than of actual population differences. As a result, there is not enough data to draw the conclusion that any of the variables significantly affects the outcome under investigation.

FINDINGS

- ❖ 58% of the sample as a whole consisted of female respondents, 42% consisted of male respondents. Just one respondents relatively tiny percentage of all respondents—identified as transgender.
- ❖ 63% of people, then employees (16%), businesses (9%), and other groups (12%). This suggests that within the surveyed population, which is mostly composed of students and a smaller proportion of workers, businesses and other sectors are underrepresented.
- ❖ The majority of responses, or 62 (41.33%), are from respondents under the age of 20, with 50 (33.33%) lying between the ages of 21 and 30. Moreover, 8 responses (5.34%) represent people over 40, and 30 responses (20%) are from people between the ages of 31 and 40.
- ❖ The respondents, 62 (41%) are married, and the majority—88 (59%)—are single. This suggests that a larger percentage of the population polled is single.
- ❖ Undergraduate (UG) students accounted for 53% of the responses, the greatest participation percentage, followed by postgraduate (PG) students at 25%. Seven percent of the replies were from high school students (HSS), and the remaining fifteen percent came from other categories.

SUGGESTIONS

- ❖ In the context of Samsung Mobile Company, this study attempts to explore the relationship between consumer behaviours, service quality, and satisfaction under intense competition in the mobile industry.
- ❖ Acknowledging that customer satisfaction is a crucial aspect in determining a company's performance, the study will examine the variables affecting consumers' attitudes and actions in order to provide insights into the problems the brand is facing.
- ❖ The study will assess consumers' perceptions of Samsung mobile devices and services' level of customer service, examining the effects on engagement, brand loyalty, and purchase decisions. It will accomplish this through benchmarking against competitors, feedback analysis, and surveys..
- ❖ Surveys, comments, and reviews can be used to gauge how satisfied customers are with Samsung's mobile goods and service.

CONCLUSION

The study will evaluate how customers see the quality of customer service provided by Samsung mobile devices and services, looking at how this affects engagement, brand loyalty, and purchase decisions. It will use surveys, feedback analysis, and benchmarking against rivals to achieve this .managing the quality of service provider and handling convenience of Samsung smartphones. The Coimbatore city study aids in identifying the advantages and disadvantages of the Samsung smartphone. It highlight the main conclusions about customer happiness with Samsung's mobile devices, including overall satisfaction levels, elements that influence satisfaction (such features, quality of the product, and customer service), any noteworthy trends or patterns, and possible areas for improvement found during the research. Even if there are many new smartphone brands available, Samsung has a strong reputation for its brand. The lifespan of a mobile phone is more than sufficient for users to utilize Samsung devices for four to five years. The cost is reasonable considering the brand and longevity of Samsung smartphones. According to this research, the majority of consumers prefer utilizing Samsung mobile devices because they come with characteristics like a strong processor, a good camera, and greater battery life. At an affordable price.

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